

Mathematics in Literature: Enhancing Learners' Proficiency in Numeracy through Illustrated Storybooks

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16900219

Christian E. Soligan

La Consolacion College Bacolod

<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9601-7541> | christian.soligan@deped.gov.ph

Abstract:

This study examined the effectiveness of illustrated mathematics storybooks in improving the numeracy proficiency of Grade 7 students in a public secondary school in Silay City, Negros Occidental, Philippines. Using an action research design, the intervention integrated four quality-assured illustrated storybooks—each contextualizing one of the four fundamental operations on integers—into mathematics lessons over four weeks. The quantitative phase involved total population sampling of 40 students, while the qualitative phase used maximum variation sampling to select six participants for in-depth interviews and classroom observations. Pretest and posttest scores were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and qualitative data were subjected to thematic analysis following Lichtman's 3Cs framework. Results indicated a notable improvement in students' proficiency levels, with qualitative findings highlighting increased engagement, better conceptual understanding, and more positive attitudes toward mathematics. The integration of literature and mathematics was found to address both cognitive and affective dimensions of learning, making abstract concepts more relatable through narrative contexts. The study recommends incorporating illustrated mathematics storybooks into classroom instruction, providing teacher training for effective implementation, and developing culturally relevant materials to enhance both literacy and numeracy outcomes.

Keywords: numeracy, mathematics education, literature integration, illustrated storybooks, integer operations, action research, contextualized learning, Philippine education

Introduction:

Mathematics is a foundational discipline that plays a critical role in achieving the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly in fostering economic growth, reducing inequality, and enhancing quality education. Sustainable Development Goal 4 emphasizes that by 2030, all youth and a substantial proportion of adults should achieve literacy and numeracy (Žalėnienė & Pereira, 2021; Vásquez et al., 2023). Numeracy, in this context, is not limited to the ability to perform basic calculations; it encompasses confidence and willingness to engage with quantitative and spatial information in order to make informed decisions in all aspects of life (Wang & Wei, 2024). It includes skills such as recognizing symbols (Russo et al., 2021; Aunio et al., 2021; Jiménez Lira et al., 2017; Raghobar & Barnes, 2016), mastering number relationships (Aunio et al., 2021; Scalisce & Purpura, 2021; Wilcox et al., 2022), and applying arithmetic operations to solve real-world problems (DepEd, 2017; Meutia et al., 2020; Rosyidah et al., 2021).

The value of numeracy extends beyond the mathematics classroom. Research shows that numeracy skills influence life outcomes, including employability, health literacy, and civic participation (Goos & O'Sullivan, 2023; Serin, 2023). Yet, across many countries, a persistent gap exists in ensuring equitable numeracy proficiency among students. Educational systems adopt varying approaches to address this challenge, from integrating numeracy into all subject areas to creating dedicated mathematics programs (Bennison & Geiger, 2020; Neema, 2025; Nahdi et al., 2021; Nityasanti et al., 2025). In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) has prioritized strengthening numeracy within the K to 12 curriculum to produce graduates who are not only job-ready but also capable of critical problem-solving (Barrot, 2021).

Despite these initiatives, evidence from national and international assessments suggests that Filipino students continue to underperform in mathematics. For instance, the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) ranked the Philippines near the bottom among participating countries in mathematical literacy (OECD, 2019). Low numeracy performance has been linked to instructional gaps, limited contextualization of mathematics content,

and insufficient opportunities for students to see the relevance of mathematics to their lives (Bernardo, 2022; Madrazo & Dio, 2020). These findings underscore the need for innovative pedagogical strategies that make mathematics meaningful, engaging, and connected to real-life experiences.

One promising approach to making mathematics more relevant is its integration with literature. Literature—whether narrative fiction, poetry, or informational text—can serve as a medium for contextualizing mathematical ideas in ways that foster deeper understanding. This approach aligns with constructivist theories, which emphasize that learning is most effective when new knowledge is built upon meaningful contexts (Vygotsky, 1978; Bruner, 1996). Through literature, abstract mathematical concepts can be embedded in stories, scenarios, or problems that mirror students' lived experiences, potentially increasing motivation and comprehension.

The integration of mathematics and literature is not without its challenges. While interdisciplinary learning has been promoted in many educational frameworks, implementing it effectively requires both teachers' confidence in mathematics instruction and their ability to select or create texts that authentically incorporate mathematical concepts (Thanheiser et al., 2014). There is also a risk of superficial integration, where literature is merely used as a decorative element without genuinely enhancing mathematical thinking (Bintz & Moore, 2018). These tensions point to the importance of careful design, professional development, and evidence-based evaluation of integrated learning approaches.

From a cognitive perspective, embedding mathematics in narrative contexts may support dual coding—engaging both verbal and visual processing systems—which can aid retention and problem-solving (Paivio, 1991; Mayer, 2001). Furthermore, literature offers a natural platform for exploring mathematical reasoning, pattern recognition, and critical thinking within the flow of a story. For example, problem scenarios in children's books or thematic literature can invite students to apply mathematical operations, interpret quantitative relationships, or engage in estimation tasks (Whitin & Whitin, 2004).

In the Philippine context, there is growing recognition that language and literacy skills influence mathematical achievement (Racca & Lasaten, 2016). Students often struggle with word problems not because they lack computational skills, but because they misinterpret the language used (Bernardo, 2022). Integrating literature into mathematics instruction may bridge this gap by simultaneously strengthening reading comprehension and numeracy. However, despite its potential, empirical research on the integration of mathematics and literature in Philippine classrooms remains limited.

There is also an equity dimension to this pedagogical approach. Integrating mathematics with literature can be particularly beneficial for learners from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Literature provides culturally responsive entry points to mathematical concepts, allowing teachers to draw on local stories, contexts, and values (English & Kirshner, 2015). This approach could be especially valuable in the Philippines, where multilingual classrooms are the norm and culturally relevant pedagogy is essential for engagement and inclusion.

Nevertheless, the potential of this integration depends on its thoughtful implementation. It requires teachers to have both mathematical content knowledge and pedagogical skills in integrating literature meaningfully. It also necessitates curricular alignment, availability of appropriate resources, and assessment strategies that capture both mathematical and literacy gains (Rincón & Munárriz, 2025). Without these supports, integration efforts may fail to achieve their intended outcomes.

Given the global and local challenges in mathematics achievement, the educational promise of interdisciplinary approaches, and the underexplored potential of integrating literature into mathematics instruction in the Philippine setting, this study seeks to investigate the integration of mathematical concepts in literature and its perceived effects on students' learning experiences. By examining how literature can serve as a contextual bridge for mathematical understanding, this research aims to contribute to the discourse on innovative, context-sensitive pedagogies that address both cognitive and affective dimensions of learning.

Methodology:

This study employed an action research design, recognized for its applied and problem-solving orientation. Action research is a systematic process in which educators identify a problem, collect and analyze relevant data, and implement changes to improve practice while investigating its effects (Mills, 2017; Creswell & Poth, 2023). It is the most practical of research designs, allowing for simultaneous investigation and intervention to address local issues (George, 2008). In this study, the researcher—also serving as the classroom teacher—implemented illustrated mathematics storybooks as an instructional intervention, with the aim of improving students' proficiency in operations involving integers. The cyclical process of planning, acting, observing, and reflecting guided the study's execution (Stringer, 2013).

The study was conducted in a public secondary high school located in the highlands of Silay City, Negros Occidental, Philippines. The school serves a rural community where most families depend on sugarcane farming for livelihood. The location was chosen for its relevance to the researcher's professional context and for the presence of Grade 7 learners who met the study's inclusion criteria.

The quantitative phase involved 40 Grade 7 students, ages 11 to 13, enrolled during the school year of the study. All students in the target class were included through total population sampling, a purposive sampling technique that involves examining an entire group sharing specific characteristics (Dudovskiy, 2022). For the qualitative phase, maximum variation sampling (Nikolopoulou, 2022) was used to select six learners—three with the highest posttest scores and three with the lowest—to capture a broad range of perspectives. Inclusion criteria required that participants be Grade 7 students, aged 11–13, and willing to participate with parental consent. The school principal served as the gatekeeper, granting formal permission to conduct the study (Andoh-Arthur, 2020).

Three instruments were employed in this study. The first was a 40-item researcher-developed numeracy test designed to assess learners' skills in addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division of integers. The test included both computational items and word problems to measure procedural fluency and problem-solving abilities. The second instrument was an interview guide consisting of open-ended questions adapted from Creswell's (2012) framework, which aimed to explore the learners' experiences and perceptions regarding the use of illustrated mathematics storybooks. The third instrument was an observation protocol based on Creswell's (2012) format, which allowed the researcher to systematically record field notes on student behaviors, engagement, and learning processes during the implementation of the intervention.

The content validity of the numeracy test was established using Lawshe's (1975) Content Validity Ratio (CVR), resulting in an overall Content Validity Index (CVI) of 0.975, which is considered excellent (Polit et al., 2007). The interview guide was validated using the framework of Good and Scates (1954). A pilot test of the numeracy test was conducted with a different group of Grade 7 students, and Kuder-Richardson Formula 21 (KR-21) yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.73, indicating strong reliability.

Trustworthiness was ensured using Lincoln and Guba's (1985) criteria—credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Credibility was enhanced through triangulation of interviews, observations, and test data, along with member checking to confirm the accuracy of interpretations (Bhandari, 2022). Transferability was addressed through thick descriptions of the research context and participants (Stalmeijer et al., 2014). Dependability was ensured through reflexivity and consistent application of data collection procedures, while confirmability was supported by maintaining an audit trail of decisions and evidence (Nowell, 2017).

Results:***Proficiency Level of Learners in Numeracy Before and After the Intervention***

The pre-intervention assessment revealed that the learners had a low proficiency in numeracy ($M = 17.83$, $SD = 5.69$), indicating that they possessed only the minimum knowledge, skills, and core understanding needed for numeracy and required assistance in performing authentic tasks. Following the use of illustrated mathematics storybooks, the learners' proficiency notably improved, achieving a "Proficient" level ($M = 30.13$, $SD = 3.70$). At this stage, learners demonstrated fundamental knowledge and core understanding of numeracy concepts and were able to apply them independently in authentic performance tasks. This substantial increase underscores the effectiveness of the illustrated mathematics storybooks in improving numeracy proficiency.

Table 2

Proficiency level of learners in numeracy before and after the intervention

	n	M	SD	Description
Before	40	17.83	5.69	Low Proficiency
After	40	30.13	3.7	Proficient

These findings are consistent with previous studies (Akıncı-Coşgun et al., 2020; Utaminingsih et al., 2022), which found that illustrated mathematics storybooks notably improve mathematics skills by presenting concepts in engaging, relatable contexts. According to Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen and Elia (2012), embedding mathematical ideas within stories connects abstract concepts to everyday life, aiding comprehension. Other researchers (Hendriana et al., 2018; Lemonidis & Kaiafa, 2019) have emphasized that storybooks also enhance motivation, reduce math anxiety, and promote critical thinking and problem-solving.

Themes from Learners’ Experiences

Analysis of the interview transcripts and observation notes revealed eight central themes that encapsulate learners’ experiences with the storybooks: (1) Engagement and Motivation, (2) Conceptual Understanding, (3) Bridging Mathematical Concepts and Practical Scenarios, (4) Developing Problem-Solving Skills and Critical Thinking, (5) Reducing Math Anxiety, (6) Visualization and Comprehension, (7) Accessibility and Ease of Learning, and (8) The Need for Structured Guidance and Reinforcement. These themes were derived from 21 clusters of relevant meaning.

Table 3

Themes from the experiences of the learners and the researchers in using the illustrated mathematics storybooks

No.	Initial Themes	Central Ideas/Themes
1	Engagement and enjoyment; making math fun and relatable; learning through characters	Engagement and Motivation: Enhancing Learners’ Interest in Integer Operations Through Storybooks
2	Conceptual understanding of integer relationships; clarifying abstract concepts; step-by-step learning; gradual mastery of concepts	Conceptual Understanding: Strengthening Learners’ Grasp of Integer Operations Through Narrative-Based Learning
3	Real-life application; engagement through contextual learning	Bridging Mathematical Concepts and Practical Scenarios Through Storytelling
4	Problem-solving approach; learning through exploration and discovery; interactive and experiential learning	Developing Problem-Solving Skills and Critical Thinking Through Story-Based Learning
5	Building confidence in math; breaking math anxiety; changing perceptions about math	Reducing Math Anxiety: Transforming Learners’ Perceptions and Self-Efficacy in Mathematics Through Storybooks
6	Visualization and comprehension; visualization of math concepts	Visualization and Comprehension: Enhancing Cognitive Processing of Integer Operations Through Narrative and Illustrations
7	Making learning more accessible; accessibility in mathematics learning	Accessibility and Ease of Learning: Making Integer Concepts More Understandable Through Engaging and Contextualized Storytelling
8	Need for additional reinforcement; structured guidance in learning	Illustrated Mathematics Storybooks: A Need for Structured Guidance and Reinforcement

Learners expressed that storybooks made learning more enjoyable and relatable, helping them understand integer operations through characters and real-life contexts. Many described improved confidence and reduced anxiety toward mathematics. Visualization through illustrations enhanced comprehension, while contextual narratives bridged abstract concepts with daily life. Some learners, however, indicated a need for additional reinforcement through guided practice and structured exercises to consolidate learning.

Themes from the Researcher's Experiences

The researcher's reflection and observation data yielded two major themes: (1) Illustrated Mathematics Storybooks as a Torch of Enlightenment, highlighting the improvement in student engagement, conceptual understanding, and the effectiveness of visual and narrative elements; and (2) Paving the Way Towards Efficacy in Teaching Mathematics, focusing on addressing conceptual challenges, the need for reinforcement strategies, and the role of discussions in deepening understanding.

Table 4

Themes from the researcher's experiences in using the illustrated mathematics storybooks

No.	Initial Themes	Central Ideas/Themes
1	Improved student interest and engagement; conceptual understanding in real-world contexts; effectiveness of visual aids and story elements	Illustrated Mathematics Storybooks: A Torch of Enlightenment
2	Challenges in learning certain operations; need for additional reinforcement strategies; role of discussions in deepening understanding	Paving the Way Towards Efficacy in Teaching Mathematics

The researcher noted that storybooks increased learner participation, contextualized mathematical concepts effectively, and utilized visuals to aid comprehension. However, to maximize effectiveness, reinforcement strategies such as peer collaboration, guided questioning, and interactive exercises were necessary.

Discussion:

The findings of this study demonstrate that the integration of illustrated mathematics storybooks into instruction notably improved the learners' numeracy proficiency, as evidenced by the increase from a low proficiency level ($M = 17.83$, $SD = 5.69$) prior to the intervention to a proficient level ($M = 30.13$, $SD = 3.70$) afterward. This aligns with the work of Kınıcı-Coşgun et al., (2020) and Utaminingsih et al. (2022), who found that illustrated mathematics storybooks promote mathematics skill development by presenting abstract concepts in accessible, engaging formats. The narratives and visual elements in such storybooks contextualize mathematical ideas, allowing learners to connect numerical operations to familiar scenarios, thereby fostering comprehension and retention (Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen & Elia, 2012).

The qualitative results further reinforce these quantitative findings by providing insights into the affective and cognitive dimensions of learning facilitated by storybooks. The themes that emerged—engagement and motivation, conceptual understanding, bridging mathematical concepts with practical scenarios, problem-solving and critical thinking development, reduction of math anxiety, visualization and comprehension, accessibility, and the need for structured guidance—mirror existing literature on the pedagogical value of storytelling in mathematics (Bhatti, 2024; Lemonidis & Kaiafa, 2019). By situating mathematical concepts within storylines, the intervention enhanced learners' motivation, transformed their perceptions of mathematics, and reduced anxiety toward the subject (Ramirez et al., 2018).

A particularly notable finding is the impact on learners' conceptual understanding. Participants described how the narrative format clarified the rules behind integer operations and allowed for step-by-step mastery, supporting Lemonidis & Kaiafa's (2019) assertion that contextualized examples enhance conceptual grasp. This is consistent with Bruner's (1996) view that meaningful learning occurs when students construct understanding through narrative rather than rote memorization. Similarly, Blinkoff et al., (2023) observed that embedding mathematical concepts in

sequential, contextualized stories enables learners to process operations as logical progressions, improving comprehension.

The results also highlight the role of storytelling in bridging abstract concepts with real-life applications. Learners reported that illustrated mathematics storybooks helped them relate integer operations to everyday experiences, echoing Boaler's (2015) emphasis on authentic contexts in mathematics instruction. Such contextualization fosters transferability of knowledge, as learners see mathematics as relevant beyond the classroom. Additionally, integrating culturally resonant narratives into mathematics supports inclusivity and representation, challenging gender stereotypes and promoting equity in mathematics engagement (Kuteesa et al., 2024).

The development of problem-solving and critical thinking skills was another prominent outcome. Consistent with Riyanto et al., (2017) and Herianingtyas et al. (2024), learners engaged in exploration, discovery, and interactive learning through story-based challenges. These activities encouraged analytical reasoning and collaborative discourse, thereby cultivating a classroom culture of inquiry.

The intervention also addressed a persistent barrier to mathematics achievement—math anxiety. Many learners reported a shift from apprehension to enjoyment, a transformation supported by Scheibe et al., (2025) and Kruger and Enriquez (2023), who found that narrative-based learning reduces anxiety and strengthens mathematical self-efficacy. By framing mathematical challenges within engaging stories, the intervention created a psychologically safe learning space, enabling learners to participate without fear of failure.

Visualization emerged as a key factor in comprehension. The integration of illustrations alongside narratives provided dual coding—verbal and visual—enhancing cognitive processing of integer operations (Fyfe et al., 2015). Learners benefited from seeing visual representations of concepts such as the number line, positive and negative integers, and real-world scenarios, supporting Paivio's (1991) dual coding theory.

Finally, while the intervention proved effective, findings indicated that some learners required additional instructional support to fully grasp certain operations, particularly division of integers. This aligns with the recommendations of Jalandoni & Futral (2024) and Bandahala (2024), who emphasize the importance of structured guidance and reinforcement alongside story-based learning. Hands-on exercises, guided discussions, and scaffolding remain essential for ensuring procedural fluency and deep conceptual understanding.

In sum, the results of this study corroborate existing evidence that illustrated mathematics storybooks serve as an effective pedagogical tool, particularly in developing engagement, conceptual clarity, problem-solving skills, and positive attitudes toward mathematics. However, optimal outcomes depend on intentional integration with structured teaching strategies, reinforcement activities, and culturally relevant materials. This dual emphasis on narrative and explicit instruction offers a balanced approach that addresses both the cognitive and affective domains of mathematics learning.

Conclusion:

This study provides empirical evidence that the use of illustrated mathematics storybooks can substantially enhance Grade 7 learners' numeracy proficiency, particularly in operations involving integers. The combination of narrative and visual elements effectively contextualized mathematical concepts, allowing students to relate abstract operations to real-life situations. The quantitative results revealed a notable improvement in proficiency levels from "Low Proficiency" prior to the intervention to "Proficient" afterward, while qualitative findings highlighted increased engagement, reduced math anxiety, and improved conceptual understanding. The intervention also fostered problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and positive attitudes toward mathematics, aligning with the theoretical perspectives on contextualized and narrative-based learning.

Moreover, the study underscores that the integration of literature and mathematics addresses both cognitive and affective aspects of learning, supporting the development of procedural fluency alongside motivation and self-efficacy. However, the results also reveal that optimal learning outcomes require structured guidance, scaffolding, and follow-up practice to reinforce mathematical skills—particularly for learners who initially demonstrated lower

proficiency. This finding indicates that while illustrated mathematics storybooks are a powerful pedagogical tool, they are most effective when implemented as part of a broader, intentional instructional strategy.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that mathematics educators incorporate illustrated mathematics storybooks as a supplementary resource to reinforce core concepts, particularly for topics that learners often find challenging, such as integer operations. Teacher training programs should include professional development on integrating storytelling into mathematics instruction to maximize the pedagogical potential of such resources. Curriculum developers are encouraged to design and provide culturally relevant and linguistically accessible storybooks that reflect learners' local contexts and lived experiences, thereby promoting inclusivity and engagement.

Furthermore, schools should consider embedding this approach within a comprehensive instructional framework that combines narrative-based learning with explicit instruction, guided practice, and formative assessment. Researchers are encouraged to replicate this study in different grade levels, subject areas, and learning environments to determine the broader applicability and long-term effects of mathematics-literature integration. Finally, policymakers should support the production, quality assurance, and dissemination of innovative instructional materials such as illustrated mathematics storybooks to strengthen both literacy and numeracy across the curriculum.

References:

Akıncı-Coşgun, A., Stites, M. L., & Sonnenschein, S. (2020). Using Storybooks to Support Young Children's Mathematics Learning at School and Home. *Development, and Education*.

Andoh-Arthur, J. (2020). *Gatekeepers in qualitative research*. SAGE Publications Ltd.

Aunio, P., Korhonen, J., Ragpot, L., Törmänen, M., & Henning, E. (2021). An early numeracy intervention for first-graders at risk for mathematical learning difficulties. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 55, 252–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2020.12.002>

Bandahala, D. E. (2024). Explicit instruction in teaching general mathematics and the application of concrete – pictorial-abstract approach. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 07(10). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v7-i10-32>

Barrot, J. S. (2021). K to 12 curriculum reform in the Philippines: Towards making students future ready. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 43(4), 1193–1207. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2021.1973959>

Bennison, A., & Geiger, V. (2020). Numeracy across the curriculum as a model of integrating mathematics and science. In *Advances in STEM Education* (pp. 117–136). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-52229-2_7

Bernardo, A. B. I., Cordel, M. O., II, Lapinid, M. R. C., Teves, J. M. M., Yap, S. A., & Chua, U. C. (2022). Contrasting profiles of low-performing mathematics students in public and private schools in the Philippines: Insights from machine learning. *Journal of Intelligence*, 10(3), 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence10030061>

Bhandari, P. (2022, January 3). Triangulation in research. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/triangulation/>

Bhatti, T. K. O. (2024). *Teachers' Perceptions of a Mathematics Intervention Implemented in Australian Secondary Schools* (pp. 1–150) [Thesis]. Institute for Sustainable Industries & Liveable Cities (ISILC).

Bintz, W. P., & Moore, S. D. (2018). Using Literature to Teach Problem Solving in Mathematics. *Ohio Journal of School of Mathematics*, 81(1).

Blinkoff, E., Nesbitt, K. T., Golinkoff, R. M., & Hirsh-Pasek, K. (2023). Investigating the contributions of active, playful learning to student interest and educational outcomes. *Acta Psychologica*, 238, 103983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2023.103983>

Boaler, J. (2015). *Mathematical mindsets: Unleashing students' potential through creative math, inspiring messages and innovative teaching*. John Wiley & Sons.

Bruner, J. (1996). *The Culture of Education*. Harvard University Press.

Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Pearson Education.

Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2023). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. SAGE Publications.

DepEd. (2017). mathematical and Problem Solving Skills. In *K-12 Basic Education Curriculum Guide* (pp. 2–60). Department of Education.

Dudovskiy, J. (2022). *The Ultimate Guide to Writing a Dissertation in Business Studies: A Step-by-Step Assistance (6th ed.)*. Research Methodology; Business Research Methodology. <http://research-methodology.net/about-us/ebook/>

English, L. D., & Kirshner, D. (2015). *Handbook of International Research in Mathematics Education*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203448946>

Etikan, I. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajtas.20160501.11>

Fyfe, E. R., McNeil, N. M., & Borjas, S. (2015). Benefits of “concreteness fading” for children’s mathematics understanding. *Learning and Instruction*, 35, 104–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2014.10.004>

George, M. W. (2008). *The Elements of Library Research: What Every Student Needs to Know*. Princeton University Press.

Good, C. V., & Scates, D. E. (1954). *Methods of research: Educational, psychological, sociological*. Appleton-Century-Crofts. <https://doi.org/10.1037/13206-000>

Goos, M., & O’Sullivan, K. (2022). *Numeracy across the curriculum*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264093.013.1530>

Hendriana, H., Johanto, T., & Sumarmo, U. (2018). The Role of Problem-Based Learning to Improve Students’ Mathematical Problem-Solving Ability and Self Confidence. *Journal on Mathematics Education*, 9(2), 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.22342/jme.9.2.5394.291-300>

Herianingtyas, N. L. R., Suryaningsih, T., Sumantri, M. S., Utomo, E., & Nurhasanah, N. (2024). How Science-Mathematics based Fairytale Book Enhance Critical Thinking Skills and Curiosity in Elementary School Students? *Al Ibtida: Jurnal Pendidikan Guru MI*, 11(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.24235/al.ibtida.snj.v11i1.15809>

Jalandoni, J. F., & Futralan, M. C. (2024). Scaffolding students’ difficulties in addition and subtraction of integers through game-based instruction. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 2(7). <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0143>

Jiménez Lira, C., Carver, M., Douglas, H., & LeFevre, J.-A. (2017). The integration of symbolic and non-symbolic representations of exact quantity in preschool children. *Cognition*, 166, 382–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2017.05.033>

Kruger, M. W., & Enriquez, G. (2023). Math and picture books: Story, math anxiety, and building joy. *The Reading Teacher*, 76(6), 735–739. <https://doi.org/10.1002/trtr.2202>

Kuteesa, K. N., Chidiogo Uzoamaka Akpuokwe, & Udeh, C. A. (2024). Gender equity in education: Addressing challenges and promoting opportunities for social empowerment. *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, 6(4), 631–641. <https://doi.org/10.51594/ijarss.v6i4.1034>

Lawshe, C. H. (1975). A quantitative approach to content validity. *Personnel Psychology*, 28(4), 563–575.

Lemonidis, C., & Kaiafa, I. (2019). The effect of using storytelling strategy on students’ performance in fractions. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 8(2), 165. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v8n2p165>

Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. SAGE.

Madrazo, A. L., & Dio, R. V. (2020). Contextualized Learning Modules in Bridging Students’ Learning Gaps in Calculus with Analytic Geometry through Independent Learning. *Journal on Mathematics Education*, 11(3), 457–476.

<https://doi.org/10.22342/jme.11.3.12456.457-476>

Mayer, R. E. (2001). *Multimedia learning*. Cambridge University Press.

Meutia, C. I., Ikhsan, M., & Saminan. (2020). Mathematical problem-solving skills of junior high school students. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1460(1), 012010. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1460/1/012010>

Mills, G. E. (2017). Action research: A guide for the teacher researcher. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 23(3).

Nahdi, D. S., Jatisunda, M. G., & Suciawati, V. (2021). Pre-service teacher's ability in solving mathematics problems viewed from Self-Resilience. *Malikussaleh Journal of Mathematics Learning (MJML)*, 4(2), 117. <https://doi.org/10.29103/mjml.v4i2.2916>

Neema, T. (2025). Strategies for improving student achievement in mathematics in grade 10 board examinations. *Journal of Humanities and Education Development*, 7(3), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.22161/jhed.7.3.1>

Nikolopoulou, K. (2022, July 20). What is Non-Probability Sampling? *Articles by Kassiani Nikolopoulou*. <https://www.scribbr.com/author/kassianin/page/11/>

Nityasanti, N., Laila, A., Saida, A., Baharudin, B., & Yasin, M. H. M. (2025). 21st Century Learning: A research analysis of numeracy literacy trends among students. *IJORER: International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 6(1), 264–277. <https://doi.org/10.46245/ijorer.v6i1.726>

Nowell, L. S., Norris, J. M., White, D. E., & Moules, N. J. (2017). Thematic analysis. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406917733847>

OECD. (2019). *PISA 2018 Results (Volume I)*. OECD Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2019/12/pisa-2018-results-volume-i_947e3529.html

Paivio, A. (1991). Dual coding theory: Retrospect and current status. *Canadian Journal of Psychology / Revue Canadienne de Psychologie*, 45(3), 255–287.

Paivio, A. (2013). *Imagery and verbal processes*. Psychology Press.

Racca, R. M. A. B., & Lasaten, R. C. S. (2016). English language proficiency and academic performance of Philippine science high school students. *International Journal of Languages, Literature and Linguistics*, 2(2), 44–49. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijll.2016.2.2.65>

Raghubar, K. P., & Barnes, M. A. (2016). Early numeracy skills in preschool-aged children: A review of neurocognitive findings and implications for assessment and intervention. *The Clinical Neuropsychologist*, 31(2), 329–351. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13854046.2016.1259387>

Ramirez, G., Shaw, S. T., & Maloney, E. A. (2018). Math anxiety: Past research, promising interventions, and a new interpretation framework. *Educational Psychologist*, 53(3), 145–164.

Rincón, Y. R., & Munárriz, A. (2025). From math aversion to effective integration: Theoretical framework for building quantitative skills in Economics and Business students. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 23(3), 101193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2025.101193>

Riyanto, B., Zulkardi, Putri, R. i I., & Darmawijoyo. (2017). Mathematical modeling in realistic mathematics education. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 943, 012049. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/943/1/012049>

Rosyidah, A. N. K., Mauluda, M. A., Jiwandono, I. S., Oktaviyanti, I., & Gunawan, G. (2021). Misconceptions and errors in integer operations: A study in preservice elementary school teachers (PGSD). *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1779(1), 012078. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1779/1/012078>

Russo, J., Bragg, L. A., & Russo, T. (2021). How primary teachers use games to support their teaching of mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 13(4), 407–419. <https://doi.org/10.26822/iejee.2021.200>

Scalisce, N. R., & Purpura, D. J. (2021). American Psychological Association. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 1–47.

- Scheibe, D. A., Was, C. A., Sidney, P. G., & Thompson, C. A. (2025). How does math anxiety affect math performance? An experimental online two-study investigation into the mechanism driving math anxiety interventions. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*.
- Serin, H. (2023). Teaching Mathematics: Strategies for Improved Mathematical Performance. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v10i3p146>
- Stalmeijer, R. E., McNaughton, N., & Van Mook, W. N. K. A. (2014). Using focus groups in medical education research: AMEE Guide No. 91. *Medical Teacher*, 36(11), 923–939. <https://doi.org/10.3109/0142159x.2014.917165>
- Stringer, E. T. (2013). *Action research*. SAGE Publications.
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International Journal of Medical Education*, 2, 53–55. <https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd>
- Thanheiser, E., Whitacre, I., & Roy, G. (2014). Mathematical content knowledge for teaching elementary mathematics: A focus on whole-number concepts and operations. *The Mathematics Enthusiast*, 11(2), 217–266. <https://doi.org/10.54870/1551-3440.1303>
- Utaminingsih, S., Andi, P., Irfai, F., & Kuzmina, A. M. (2022). Development of Video-Aided Storybooks to Improve Understanding of Mathematical Concepts in Elementary School. *Iasa'í Yniversitetiniñ Habarshysy*, 124(2), 194–206.
- van den Heuvel-Panhuizen, M., & Elia, I. (2012). Developing a framework for the evaluation of picturebooks that support kindergartners' learning of mathematics. *Research in Mathematics Education*, 14(1), 17–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14794802.2012.657437>
- Vásquez, C., Alsina, Á., Seckel, M. J., & García-Alonso, I. (2023). Integrating sustainability in mathematics education and statistics education: A systematic review. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 19(11), em2357. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/13809>
- Vygotsky, L. S., & Cole, M. (1978). *Mind in society: Development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Wang, X., & Wei, Y. (2024). The influence of parental involvement on students' math performance: A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1463359>
- Whitin, D. J., & Whitin, P. (2004). *New visions for linking literature and mathematics*. National Council of Teachers of English (Ncte).
- Wilcox, G., MacMaster, F. P., & Makarenko, E. (2022). *Cognitive neuroscience foundations for school psychologists*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003088806>
- Žalėnienė, I., & Pereira, P. (2021). Higher education for sustainability: A global perspective. *Geography and Sustainability*, 2(2), 99–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geosus.2021.05.001>